

Anemia among Patients on Hemodialysis and Response to Hematinic Agents in a Tertiary Care Hospital of Assam, India

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Abstract:

Background: Medical practitioners and researchers must prioritize research on anemia because it significantly impacts hemodialysis patients' overall prognosis and quality of life.

Objective: This study set out to address this by collecting data on the frequency of anemia in hemodialysis patients and comparing the effectiveness of different iron, folic acid, and erythropoietin regimens in treating anemia in tertiary care hemodialysis patients.

Hypothesis: When it comes to treating anemia, we anticipate that hematinic medications will work for many hemodialysis patients suspected of having the condition.

Materials & methods: Lakhimpur Medical College and Hospital (LMCH), located in North Lakhimpur, Assam, was where this retrospective study with a cross-sectional design was carried out. The Dialysis Register and Case sheet kept at the dialysis unit of LMCH was the primary source of documented information for patients who have had hemodialysis between 1st January 2021, and, 31st December 2023. For this study, fifty patients diagnosed with chronic renal disease and who presented with anemia was included.

Results: During the research, fifty patients were incorporated into the investigation at various times. With a mean age of 48.3 years and a standard deviation of 2.54 years, their ages ranged from 15 to 70[years]. The mean age fell somewhere in the middle. The total number of individuals consisted of 31 males, which constitute 62% of the total, and 19 females, which constitutes 38% of the total. Before therapy, the mean mean corpuscular hemoglobin was determined to be 32.54 ± 3.3 ; after treatment, it climbed to 34.21 ± 1.8 respectively. This improvement was statistically significant since its p-value was lower than 0.05, indicating that it was noteworthy. When comparing the changes in other hematological parameters that occurred before and after treatment with the hematinic combination (iron, folic acid, and EPO), there is no statistically significant difference between the two data sets.

Conclusion: In addition to highlighting the efficiency of hematinic drugs, the study reveals the prevalence of anemia and its implications in patients undergoing hemodialysis. Future research might investigate the impacts over a more extended time and customize treatment options.

Keywords: Anemia; Hemodialysis; Hematinic agents; Erythropoietin; End-stage renal disease; Treatment regimen.

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Introduction

Patients who are having hemodialysis, which is a treatment that is life-sustaining for people who

have end-stage renal disease, are more susceptible to experiencing anemia as a side effect [1–4]. There

must be extensive research on the impact of anemia on hemodialysis patients' prognoses and quality of life since this condition may significantly impact these variables. Additional research is needed to determine the most effective treatment regimens for anemia in hemodialysis patients. However, hematinic medications like iron and erythropoietin have shown some promise in this regard [2-6]. Patients who are suffering from renal failure have a wide range of hematinic requirements. The specifications for iron and erythropoietin are of the utmost crucial significance. The therapy itself (the dialyzer and bloodlines retain blood in the body), having circulation pulled for lab tests and operations, losing blood inadvertently (vascular access), and losing blood via their intestines are all factors that contribute to the loss of iron that hemodialysis patients experience daily [1]. Chronic kidney disease (CKD) patients who take erythropoiesis-stimulating agents (ESAs) have a higher risk of developing iron deficiency. This is because their bodies require more iron to maintain erythropoiesis properly. According to research [2,3], the most common reason ESA medication does not perform as effectively in patients undergoing dialysis is iron shortage. Despite the broad availability of hematinic medicines, a significant number of patients on hemodialysis continue to suffer from anemia. However, no agreement exists on this condition's most effective therapy method [3,4].

Multiple studies, such as meta-analyses and systematic reviews of RCTs, have underlined the significance of these characteristics [4,5]. Along with the hematinic drugs already mentioned, vitamin B12 and folic acid are also given to these individuals to help with their condition [5,7,8]. People who have haemolysis often have hyperhomocysteinemia, a condition that raises the risk of cardiovascular disease. Folic acid, when administered at pharmaceutical doses, may mitigate this risk. [9,10,11]. Iron, folic acid, and erythropoietin are the three hematinic medications that have not been the subject of any study that examines their impact on dialysis-dependent patients with renal failure. Consequently, filling this knowledge gap is the driving force behind our investigation. Suppose we want to enhance patient outcomes and quality of life while they are on hemodialysis. In that case, we need to know what causes their anemia and how their bodies react to hematinic medications [4,5].

This study aims to answer two questions: how common is anemia among hemodialysis patients? and how do tertiary care patients respond to hematinic agents? Because of this, the researchers set out to discover how common anemia is among hemodialysis patients and how well the hematinic combination—iron, folic acid, and EPO—treats

anemia in tertiary care hemodialysis patients. We hypothesize that a sizable percentage of hemodialysis patients suspected of having anemia would respond well to treatment with hematinic medicines.

Materials & Methods

Lakhimpur Medical College and Hospital (LMCH), located in North Lakhimpur, Assam, was where this retrospective study with a cross-sectional design was carried out. The Dialysis Register and Case sheet kept at the dialysis unit of LMCH served as the primary source of documented information for patients who have had hemodialysis between January 1, 2021, and December 31, 2023. For this study, fifty patients diagnosed with chronic renal disease and who presented with anemia was included. All of the patients were given a medication that consisted of a combination of iron, folic acid, and EPO after other potential causes of anemia had been eliminated and treated. Their complete blood count was performed on a Horiba ABX micro 60 part Hematology analyzer to determine their baseline characteristics. The subcutaneous administration of about 10,000 international units of EPO, and 100 milligram elemental iron, and 500 microgram of folic acid [orally] was performed on each patient. In the sixth week, a complete blood count was performed. For up to six months, the records of patients having dialysis were monitored to see how they responded to hematinic. Some of the criteria that were investigated were age, gender, serum creatinine, hemoglobin, and the outcomes of the patients, such as whether or not they were undergoing dialysis, receiving a transplant, referred to another hospital, dying, or defaulting on their treatment.

Statistical Analysis: It was then put into Microsoft Excel 2021, which contains the information gathered from the Registers. The data that was entered was examined to see whether or not there were any gaps. An analysis of descriptive data was carried out using SPSS Version 21. The findings were explained by expressing them in terms of percentages and frequencies.

Results

In the study, fifty patients were included in the investigation at various times. With a mean age of 48.3 years and a standard deviation of 2.54 years, their ages varied from 15 to 70. The mean age fell somewhere in the middle. The total number of individuals consisted of 31 males, which constitute 62% of the total, and 19 females, which constitutes 38% of the total. In the group of patients under consideration, the average urea levels were 112 ± 9.81 .

A positive hepatitis C test was revealed in 26 people, which is equivalent to 52 percent of the total. As an additional point of interest, the mean values of hematological parameters are provided in Table 1 both before and after medication administration. Based on the examination of these hematological parameters, it is evident that there has been a considerable improvement in the concentration of hemoglobin. The hemoglobin concentration has risen from 7.9 ± 0.9 to 9.1 ± 0.8 , with a p value of less than 0.001, suggesting a

significant improvement. Before therapy, the mean MCH was determined to be 32.54 ± 3.3 ; after treatment, it climbed to 34.21 ± 1.8 respectively. This improvement was statistically significant since its p-value was lower than 0.05, indicating that it was noteworthy. It has been shown that there is no statistically significant difference between the changes that took place in other hematological parameters before and after treatment with the hematinic combination (iron, folic acid, and EPO). They happened before and after the therapy.

Table 1: Details of the parameters before and after treatment of hemodialysis subjects of the study

	Before treatment (n=50)	After treatment (n=50)	P Value
Hemoglobin (Hb; gm/dl)	7.9 ± 0.9	9.1 ± 0.8	< 0.001
Total leukocyte count (TLC; $\times 10^9/L$)	4.22 ± 0.09	4.3 ± 0.7	= 0.42
Platelet count ($\times 10^9/L$)	178 ± 4.61	179 ± 4.11	= 0.25
MCV (fl)	92.44 ± 2.47	93.40 ± 4.15	= 0.16
MCH (pg)	32.54 ± 3.3	34.21 ± 1.8	< 0.05
MCHC (gms/dl)	35.30 ± 4.25	36.44 ± 5.1	= 0.22

It is shown in Table 1 that the mean and p values of all of the hematological parameters were determined both before and after therapy with the hematinic combination, which consisted of iron, folic acid, and EPO.

Moreover, it demonstrates how severe the anemia was in both groups. Before receiving therapy with the hematinic combination (iron, folic acid, and EPO), as indicated in Figure 1, 44% of patients had hemoglobin levels that were lower than 8 g/dl. After receiving treatment, this proportion decreased to

8%, comprised of four individuals. In addition, 47 patients (or 94% of the total) achieved a hemoglobin level of more than 8 g/dl after receiving a hematinic combination treatment (iron, folic acid, and EPO).

The post-treatment hemoglobin levels of all patients were more than 7 g/dl, and no patient in the treated group had a level lower than 10 g/dl. According to the platelet count, only nine people were below 140,000/ μ l. No one in the study had either leukocytosis or leukopenia.

Figure 1: Anemia in hemodialysis patients of the study

Discussion

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is a progressive illness that significantly increases the risk of mortality and disability over time. Anemia stands

alone as a risk factor for mortality in this patient population.

Hematological alterations in patients with chronic kidney disease (CKD) have been the subject of research [1–10]. The illness worsens with time, and

anemia is one of the most prevalent signs [1-3]. Anemia was twice as common in people with chronic kidney disease (CKD) as it was in the general population. It became noticeably more common as the illness advanced, according to studies on CKD patients [5–11]. Suppose these people do not receive treatment for their anemia. In that case, they may have a decline in their heart function, a reduction in their cognitive and mental sharpness, weariness, and potentially other signs and symptoms of anemia. Every one of these issues, particularly those that are related to the heart, makes a significant contribution to the increased risk of morbidity and death that these patients currently face. Therefore, providing these patients with comprehensive treatment and monitoring them for their anemia severity is of the utmost importance. Among the several therapeutic alternatives available for chronic kidney disease (CKD) anemia, red blood cell transfusions, therapy of the underlying cause, and the utilization of erythropoietin are all examples.

This research was conducted to determine the impact that the hematinic combination, which consisted of iron, folic acid, and EPO, had on various hematological parameters, with a particular emphasis on hemoglobin. According to the data that was available, male gender was shown to be a risk factor for chronic kidney disease (CKD). This finding aligns with the fact that most of our patients are male.

We observed that the hemoglobin levels of our patients were relatively low, with a range that stretched from 5.5 ± 1.2 to 8.6 ± 0.9 at the highest possible value. The hemoglobin values that other studies have reported are comparable to those we found; these investigations highlight normochromic normocytic anemia [5-11]. Since they did not see any significant changes in other hematological parameters compared to the control group, our findings were equivalent to those we found in our study.

We found a significant rise in hemoglobin levels in our patients due to therapy with the hematinic combination, which consisted of iron, folic acid, and EPO. A p-value demonstrated this. Over the three-week follow-up, the outcomes for the patients were quite positive. The administration of erythropoietin resulted in a considerable rise in hemoglobin and hematocrit levels, according to the findings of an additional inquiry that was carried out by a study [12].

In most patients who participated in the trial, the researchers saw a significant rise in their hemoglobin levels within three months over the eight-month follow-up period. An increase in erythropoietin dosage was necessary for one of their patients, who reacted favourably to managing

the condition. In addition, every one of their patients exhibited a significant improvement in their general health, which did not appear to affect their blood pressure or any other complications.

A similar set of findings was reported by Abraham et al. [13], who stated that there was a significant improvement in both the overall condition of the patients and the quality of their lives, which ultimately led to a decrease in the number of cardiovascular problems and the death rate among patients. Twelve of our patients received erythropoietin using the subcutaneous route of administration. Numerous studies have demonstrated that how the medication is administered affects the reaction. Not only does the subcutaneous injection of EPO have a longer duration of effect than the intravenous administration, but it also requires lower quantities of the drug than the intravenous delivery [13].

Another research [14] on the hematological pattern of patients with chronic renal failure found that the majority of the participants ($n=47$) in our study had a moderate degree of anemia (hemoglobin between 7 and 10 g/d). This represents a significant difference from the findings of the previous research. [2,10]. Anemia was found to be present in 98% of patients with chronic renal failure (CRF), with 58 of those patients having significant anemia.

According to research, approximately 58 of them have normocytic normochromic anemia [15]. It was also shown that there was a significant relationship between the severity of the condition and the degree of anemia present [15]. Compared to other hematological parameters, our investigation revealed that about nine individuals, which accounts for 18% of the total, had a platelet count lower than $140,000/\mu\text{l}$. Comparisons may be made between these findings and those obtained from previous research [2,10,14].

Seventy-six percent of our patients were hypertensive, and fifty percent of them were diabetic. Anemia was a condition that almost all of them had due to the sickness. According to research, erythropoiesis-stimulating medicines, blood pressure management, and blood sugar regulation can slow the course of chronic kidney disease. Patients receiving iron replacement therapy should be evaluated monthly to guarantee that the erythropoietin medication is being prescribed appropriately.

Despite this, there is a continuing discussion over the target hemoglobin concentration, which refers to the concentration of hemoglobin that ought to be targeted to achieve the most significant possible advantages while minimizing the potentially harmful effects [7,9,12].

Furthermore, multiple studies [16,17] have revealed that cardiovascular events may be connected with pursuing and maintaining hemoglobin concentrations at highly increased levels (as a result of hypertension and thrombosis). This is, although there are no conclusive rules. The current recommendations for managing anemia in chronic renal illness imply that hemoglobin concentrations should be maintained at around 11 g/d [16,17]. By implementing the following guidelines, a trustworthy review can maximize the use of erythropoietin in patients suffering from chronic renal failure (CRF). The studies [13,16,17] suggest beginning therapy with EPO at a hematocrit of thirty percent or below, or based on anemic symptoms, and aiming for a hematocrit of roughly thirty-five percent. When giving EPO, the subcutaneous route is the most suitable option. In addition to regularly monitoring blood pressure and investigating the reasons for hypo responsiveness, it is important to identify and correct any existing iron shortage [18].

Conclusion

The research demonstrates the incidence of anemia among hemodialysis patients and the consequences of this condition, and it also highlights the efficiency of hematinic medications in the treatment of this issue. This study was conducted within the framework of tertiary care. In the hypothetical future research on this topic, the long-term effects of hematinic medicines on the treatment of anemia in patients receiving hemodialysis will be explored. Personalized therapy regimens based on each patient's specific characteristics might also be studied for their potential effectiveness.

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